

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IS THE PRIORITY DIRECTION OF OUR COUNTRY'S ECONOMY

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Abstract: The current stage of economic reforms implemented in our country requires the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, giving it wide economic freedom and improving its efficiency. To achieve this goal, the development of several decrees and decisions by the head of our country will serve to increase the efficiency of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Key words: Business, Economic indicators, e-commerce, GDP, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlarning bugungi bosqichi kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish, unga keng iqtisodiy erkinlik berish va samaradorligini oshirishni taqozo etmoqda. Bu maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun davlatimiz rahbarining bir qancha farmon va qarorlari ishlab chiqilishi kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlari samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Biznes, Iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar, elektron tijorat, YaIM, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: Современный этап экономических реформ, реализуемых в нашей стране, требует развития малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства, предоставления ему широкой экономической свободы и повышения его эффективности. Достижению этой цели разработка ряда указов и решений главой нашей страны, безусловно, послужит повышению эффективности малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства.

Ключевые слова: Бизнес, Экономические показатели, электронная коммерция, ВВП, устойчивое развитие.

Continue institutional and structural reforms aimed at further development and liberalization of the economy, strengthening macroeconomic stability and maintaining high economic growth rates, increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, modernization and rapid development of agriculture, and reducing state participation in the economy. to protect the right of private property and further strengthen its priority position, to stimulate the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, to develop regions, districts and cities in a comprehensive and balanced socio-economic way, to improve the investment environment, and to attract foreign investments to the sectors and regions of our country's economy and active involvement". Complex measures implemented to further improve the business environment in our country allow rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship and ensure stable economic growth. ^[1]

It should be noted that during the years of independence, a stable legal framework was created in Uzbekistan, which strengthens the priority of private property, which is the basis of the market economy. A favorable

business environment and reliable legal guarantees have been created for the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is an important factor for the formation of the middle owner class, the stable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the increase of the population's income.

As a result, in the last ten years, the share of small businesses in the GDP increased from 31.1% to 52.5%, the level of employment in this sector increased from 49.7% to 74.5% of the total number of employed people in economic sectors. More than 47 percent of the population's income is accounted for by income from business activities.^[2]

By the State Program "Year of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship", complex measures were taken this year to create a more favorable business environment for the wide development of entrepreneurship.

The procedure for state registration of business entities and their connection to engineering and communication networks has been significantly simplified and this process has become more transparent. The rate of state duty for registration has been halved. The list of types of activities that can be engaged in by small enterprises with an annual average number of employees increased to 100 people has been significantly expanded. A mechanism for large-scale involvement of small business entities in the process of public procurement was developed and implemented.

Measures were taken to sharply reduce the interference of state and control agencies in the financial and economic activities of enterprises and to significantly expand the economic freedom and rights of business entities. The period of exemption of newly established small enterprises and micro-firms from scheduled tax audits has been extended from two years to three years. It was forbidden to conduct tax audits for three years in small business entities that pay taxes and other mandatory payments on time, as well as ensure stable growth rates and profitability of production.^[3]

The level of capitalization of commercial banks is increasing, and the mechanism of preferential lending to small business entities, especially for their purchase of high-tech equipment, has been improved.

At the same time, several of problems that prevent the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship and limit the freedom of entrepreneurial activity remain unresolved.

The administrative regulation clearly defining the relations of business entities with the state, tax and control agencies, and commercial banks has not been fully developed. Many authorization procedures that are not transparent are still in place. There are cases of illegal interference of control agencies in the activities of business entities. A practical mechanism for exporting small business products to regional and world markets has not been created.

To further fundamentally improve the business environment, to accelerate the liberalization and deepening of market reforms, to give more freedom to entrepreneurship, to eliminate obstacles and barriers to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, to promote the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country to increase its role and share in the economy, develop export potential, ensure employment and income of the population:

1. The following should be considered important tasks of the Cabinet of Ministers, ministries, departments, economic associations, commercial banks, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional, city and district hokims:
 - elimination of excessive bureaucratic obstacles and pitfalls for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, implementation of concrete measures to reduce the functions of state administration and give more freedom to entrepreneurship, various permits implemented by state administration bodies a sharp reduction in issuance standards and restrictions;
 - ensuring openness and transparency in the interaction of business entities with state administration agencies, tax and control structures, by gradually transitioning the reporting system and the mechanism of submitting reports to finance, tax and statistics agencies to their electronic system submission radical simplification;
 - providing small business and private business entities with additional benefits and preferences that help to rapidly develop business activity and increase its efficiency in terms of tax, customs and other payments;
 - further improvement and simplification of the mechanism of interaction of small business and private business entities with commercial banks, improvement of the quality of service to business entities, loans allocated to them, first of all, for the organization of new production facilities, modernization of existing production facilities and technological increase the volume of long-term loans for renewal;
 - creation of favorable conditions for the wide participation of small business and private business entities in foreign economic activities, support for the export of their products to foreign markets, simplification and liberalization of the process of registration of export contracts and customs administration in general.

2. It should be noted that the principle of the priority of entrepreneurs' rights is followed in the interaction of business entities at all levels with state administration agencies, law enforcement and control bodies, and commercial banks, that is, by it, the elimination of All conflicts and uncertainties are interpreted in favor of entrepreneurs.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with the Ministry of Justice, and other interested ministries and agencies, should carefully develop proposals for changes and additions to the current legal documents, which provide for the establishment of the principle of the priority of the rights of entrepreneurs in them, and Submit to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.[4]

Cabinet of Ministers "About the Agency for the Development of Small Business and Entrepreneurship under the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Support for Entrepreneurial Activities

"On approval of the regulations on the state fund," It is a competent state body in the field of attracting broad classes to engage in business, expanding and improving the efficiency of the system of providing access to initial capital sources. The agency reports on its activities to the Ministry of Economy and Industry. The agency is a structural unit of the ministry and is part of its system. Coordination, control and overall management of the Agency's activities and strengthening of its material and technical base is carried out by the Ministry.

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